

TO MY PEASANT GRANDMOTHER

Rozimannopova Rohilakhan
a student of Izboskan district 16 general secondary school.

My grandmother wanders the field,
Getting up earlier than the sun.
My grandmother never gets tired
All cotton rows are walking.

He never puts down his hoe,
"The hoe is my confidant."
Even when the sun sets, she doesn't stop.
" I Give beauty to cotton" she says

Maybe the farmer's wife today
He really cares about the pain of the people.
When she is sixty-five,
Non-stop four seasons.

"If there is wheat in the house,
"One sadness will disappear," he says.
"Idleness, laziness
As a matter of fact, people grow old," he says.

"Once upon a time there was bread
"He fed fourteen souls," he says.
If the threshing floor is plentiful,
Every farmer with a bright face.

They collect their food,
How many people are in this field?
For my fellow villagers,
"Raise a big threshing floor."

The shoulder hoe is actually
Responsibility is a burden.
A woman walking in the fields-
His heart is like heaven.

TODAY

You say that one day the problem will go away
Everything is tracked
You say that one day the debts will be canceled
Another day the house will be taken

You can't be as young as today
As soon as those times come
There is no enthusiasm, like today
Happiness is in the field of life

The best day is today
Get started today
Towards the goal, towards the height
Then take the first step

Good luck tomorrow
Don't wait for an opportunity, my love
Reach your goal

Know that the best day is today.

MOTHER

You are always on my way
You yourself are a balm for my pain
I feel your sorrows
I love you mom
I live without a heart
Even if I get dressed, you don't care about me
You don't need me every second
I love you mom
If you don't have snow in your hair
Your eyes will light up when you see my happiness
I will always be loved by you
I love you mom
I'm sorry if he pulls my leg
If you leave, my friend is my enemy
Please don't stop me
I love you mom
I have a lake in cocktails
A paradise garden at its feet
My great honor in my heart
I love you mom
Stranger is infinite - he is a great responsibility
A divine blessing for a child
Your existence is wisdom
I love you mom.

THE POWER OF PRAYER

Blessed in every work,
Your efforts are in vain.
Good luck to you
May your parents bless you.

This duo is priceless
A dice whose value cannot be measured.
Don't look for luck
May your parents bless you.

It is a loss that no one can deliver
A bird of happiness always lands on the head.
You will come out of the fire alive
May your parents bless you.

Know man, whichever way you walk,
Your child will follow the same path.
Your luck won't go away,
May your parents bless you.

TO MY FIRST TEACHER

He taught us the alphabet by holding our hands,
When we came to school for the first time.
My first mentor is named after you,
Our endless love, our garden of hearts.

Always caring like our father
You were kind like our mother.
Calling for goodness and goodness
Your advice is always in our ears.

The words "Motherland, Mother" have meaning
We wrote it in our heart, teacher.
When we are happy, we are happy, when we cry, we cry.
You have become our mentor.

Even the whites in your hair
We are sorry, teacher.
You explained the meaning of life
We will always honor you.

BECAUSE OF US

Today more...
You give yourself beauty
Live in reality:
What I did for the country?
A big garden for the motherland
Don't do it
let one tree grow
Because of you.

This tree also bears fruit
Slowly.
Even if he sits in the shadow
Blessing is appointed.

Don't go to the world, to the worlds

Don't go out.

Let one person be happy

Because of you.

SPRING

Always after dark nights,

Bright days are sure to come.

Spring is knocking on the door,

Wind is blowing softly.

Leaving the cold day behind,

Spring spreads freshness.

Purple tulips today,

Covers the hills again.

Almond, apricot blossom

Is your beautiful magic spring?

The song of the swallow in the morning

Are you kind to us spring?

It rains and then the sun comes out

In the sky a rainbow congratulate you.

Good intentions with dreams

My moms can do sumalak.

When it enters every heart

Snow melts, dust washes away.

Even to hearts as hard as stone

Spring gives new life

SPRING HAS COME

A soft breeze blows my chest,
The dew kissed the face of the grass,
The cloud slowly shed tears,
Spring has come to my country again!
Smile like a primrose,
The birds are chirping,
The ground is always feeling beautiful
Spring has come to my country again!
A person in a rainbow colored dress,
Swallows dance in the blue
The heart of my pen is overflowing,
Spring has come to my country again.
This is my dream - there is a strange secret,
Once he spreads a dowry like a bride,
The rain is slow to say the least
Spring has come to my country again.
Draining the water in the ditches,
Hiding a bud in his bosom,
The farmer's spirit increased
Spring has come to my country again!
Winter is also looking forward
Almonds are the first to send a bouquet
The streets are full of flowers, the roads are mixed
Spring has come to my country again!

WONDERFUL WORLD

It's an interesting world

It's a strange world.

Never filled

There is at least one.

Everything in the world

seems to end

It will last forever

The least of the world.

People are interesting

They are one world.

Inside the houseworm

so others.

From one cup today

As if drinking soup

To one's grave

One remains a stone.